

ION EXCHANGE BEHAVIOUR OF RESORCINOL-FORMALDEHYDE RESIN

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The exchange capacity of the acid-catalysed and thoroughly cured (20 hrs. at 100°-110°) resorcinol-formaldehyde resin was determined both by analytical and potentiometric titration methods for finer fractions, the fineness extending up to colloidal range. The results of a number of determinations for different particle sizes of the resin suspensions show a limiting value close to 1220 m.e. per 100 g of the resin, representing the theoretical value on the assumption that the exchange spots (two -OH groups in this case) are hydrate. The limiting value was found to be the same irrespective of the valency of the cations adsorbed. Also, it was possible to identify the two -OH groups by a small but definite inflexion at the middle of such titration curves.

The exchange isotherms show definite inflexions in the curves obtained, indicating that the ions are held with different intensities of adsorption on the resin surface corresponding to the two -OH groups in the resorcinol unit and also indicate that the bivalent cations are more firmly held on to the resin surface than the monovalent cations.

According to the structure of the phenol-formaldehyde resins postulated by Houwink ("Physik. Eigenschaften und Teinbaue von Natur und Kunstharzen", p. 119, 134) and accepted by later investigators, the functional groups are supposed to remain intact after polymerisation. It is therefore possible to bring these groups into reaction with added reagents. Depending upon the nature of the reacting groups, the method of investigation may be modified in order to characterise the group or groups. Thus, for instance, the acid form of the phenol-formaldehyde resin can be potentiometrically titrated and from the inflexions, the nature of the hydrogen ions associated with the resin may be roughly estimated. It is further assumed that the functional groups are spatially unhindered and are accessible from all sides. To render this and to make the assumption safer, the resins may be taken in the colloidal form.

The present investigation is concerned with the study of the exchange behaviour including potentiometric curves of resorcinol-formaldehyde resin which is supposed to have two functional groups.

EXPERIMENTAL

The resin was prepared according to the method of Adams and Holmes (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1935, 54, 11). The loose, soft aggregates of the washed and cured (at 100°-110° for 10 hrs.) resin were broken by light grinding. The colloidal fractions of the resin were isolated by allowing aqueous suspensions of the -200 mesh resin to settle for 20 hours and 8 hours respectively and syphoning the materials remaining above a height of 7 cm. In order to ensure complete removal of bases, these were first collected in *N*/20-HCl medium. The suspension was afterwards filtered through sintered glass, washed free of HCl and resuspended in conductivity water.

Procedure.—The interaction between the acid resin and alkali was followed potentiometrically as well as by direct chemical determination. From a knowledge of the

exchange capacity, thus obtained, it was possible to saturate fine suspensions, *i.e.* to form 'Resinates', with different cations by adding equivalent amounts of the bases to the resin systems and allowing them to attain equilibrium. The saturating cations were then exchanged with several other different cations.

Sodium was estimated either gravimetrically (Barber and Kolthoff, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 1625) as triple acetate, $\text{NaZn}(\text{UO}_2)_2 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}_2)_6$, or volumetrically (Dobbing and Byrd, *ibid.*, 1931, 53, 3288) by titrating the solution of the triple acetate with standard alkali using phenolphthalein as an indicator. Barium was determined as BaSO_4 . Calcium was precipitated as calcium oxalate and titrated in presence of H_2SO_4 with a standard KMnO_4 solution. Ammonium ion was estimated after nesslerisation by comparing the colour developed with a standard ammonium chloride solution. A Leeds and Northrup type K potentiometer was used for E.M.F. measurements.

Exchange of Cations adsorbed from Bases.—The alkali adsorption was studied by adding an excess of standard alkali in weighed amounts of the resin kept in well-stoppered Jena bottles. The mixtures were shaken for definite periods in an end-to-end shaker. After allowing the solid matters to settle, an aliquot portion of the supernatant alkali was titrated with acid using a suitable indicator. The amount of alkali taken up by the resin was expressed in milliequivalents (m.e.) per 100 g. of it. All precautions were taken to prevent entry of CO_2 . The supernatant liquids were generally coloured (Gupta, Bose and Mukherjee, *J. Phys. & Coll. Chem.*, 1950, 54, 1098) owing perhaps to the solubilisation of a portion of the resin in presence of alkali. On account of the colour of the solution Wesselow's mixed indicator (p_n 5.0-6.5) and bromothymol blue (p_n 6.0-7.6) were used for titration. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Wt. of 100 mesh resin.	0.0925 N NaOH.	Exchange capacity with	
		Wesselow's indicator.	(B.T.B.) indicator.
0.0322 g.	50 e.c.	924 m.e.	1215 m.e.
0.0329	100	905	...
0.0589	50	942	1330
0.0586	100	877	1294
0.0944	50	917	...

Phenolphthalein was, however, a suitable indicator if barium and calcium hydroxides were used for adsorption and subsequent titrations. This is due to the fact that the bivalent ions keep the highly dispersed but slightly solubilised resin in a coagulated state. The results obtained with a 200 mesh sample are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Expt. No.	Wt. of resin.	Exchange capacity (m.e.)
1	0.2232 g.	1160 [$\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$]
2	0.9460	1360 [$\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$]

In this connection, experiments of Akeroyd and Broughton (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1938, 42, 343) may be mentioned in which they observed as high as 3600 m.e. exchange capa-

city of the bifunctional resin - using $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$. They suggested that lime was probably taken up as $-\text{CaOH}$. While this possibility is not ignored, it is not borne out by the present work. It must be mentioned that a small error was introduced in the above experiments in not taking sufficient precautions against carbon dioxide of the air.

Potentiometric Titration of the Supernatant Solution of the Alkali-treated Resin.—Partly because the supernatant liquid containing the dispersed portion of the resin, was too much coloured to enable accurate indicator method of colorimetric titration and partly because it was difficult to select a suitable indicator, the excess of alkali was potentiometrically titrated. For this purpose, a sample of resin, cured for 10 hours, was taken in a 250 c.c. Jena bottle and after addition of 75 c.c. of an approximately $N/10$ - NaOH solution and shaken in an end-to-end shaker for 12 hours. The mixture was then

allowed to settle for a day and 10 c.c. of the supernatant liquid was withdrawn into the titration vessel containing an excess of H_2SO_4 of known strength (approx. $0.1 N$). The excess of the acid, was then potentiometrically titrated with NaOH using quinhydrone electrode. Therefore we are dealing here with a mixture of H_2SO_4 and a much weaker acid, *i.e.* hydrogen resin, for titration. The neutralisation points are better shown up by the buffer capacity curve (Fig. 1); the two peaks in this curve besides that of H_2SO_4 correspond to the neutralisation of the resin. This, as will be shown later, is an important characteristic of this resin. In the experiment 0.0834 g. of the resin was treated with 75 c.c. of $0.1069 N$ - NaOH , 10 c.c. of the supernatant

solution was added to 10 c.c. of $0.1082 N$ - H_2SO_4 and the mixture required 1.32 c.c. of $0.1069 N$ - NaOH for neutralisation, corresponding to the second peak. On evaluation exchange capacity comes out to be equal to 1153 m.e. per 100 g. of the resin.

FIG. 1

DISCUSSION

The Significance of the Exchange Capacity.—According to Houwink's picture the structural unit of the resorcinol-formaldehyde resin may be represented as

The two (-OH) groups represent those belonging to the resorcinol unit which, since they do not take part in the condensation, remain intact. They are considered as the exchange spots on the resin. The linkages to other units of the structure take place through the methylene groups which are shared by two such adjacent units. Assuming that all the -OH groups are available for exchange, each unit having a weight of 128 g. ($C_6H_2O_2 + \frac{1}{2}CH_2$, only half of each $-CH_2-$ group being considered as part of each unit) will contain therefore 2 equivalents. Calculating on the basis of 100 g. of the resin, the exchange capacity becomes equal to 1560 m.e.

In none of the experiments including those to be presented later on, a value as high as 1560 m.e. could be attained. If, however, we assume that the H^+ ions on the exchange spots of the oven-dried resin (105°) exist not as H^+ but as H_3O^+ ion, the calculated exchange capacity becomes equal to 1220 m.e., a value close to the observed highest values. The existence of H_3O^+ ions in aqueous solutions of acids is now well established. It has been shown that in the case of colloidal clay acids the hydrogen ions are possibly present as H_3O^+ ions (Ganguli and Gupta, *Science & Culture*, 1948, 14, 81). Existence of H_3O^+ ions in exchange resins has also been suggested by Boyd *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 2818) in order to explain the easy exchange of hydrogen ions from the Amberlite IR-1, studied by them.

Exchange Capacity from the Direct Estimation of the Adsorbed Cation.—Instead of determining the amount of caustic soda consumed by the resin, the amount of sodium adsorbed by the resin may be directly estimated. For this purpose approximately 1 g. of the 10 hour-cured, 200 mesh sample of the resin was thoroughly shaken with an excess of 0.1N-NaOH for 12 hours, the total contact being 48 hours. This was then filtered through a Gooch crucible and leached with a further quantity of 0.1N-NaOH solution in order to completely replace the H^+ ions with Na^+ . The Na-resin, thus formed, was washed several times with alcohol which had been neutralised with NaOH. The Gooch with its contents was dried at 105° and the dry Na-resin lightly powdered. Portions of this Na-resin were then treated with 0.5N-HCl and shaken for 12 hours. The resin after filtration through a Gooch was further leached with 0.5N-HCl to completely replace the adsorbed Na^+ . The Na^+ in the hydrochloric acid leachate was then estimated by titrating the sodium zinc uranyl acetate with NaOH. From the amount of sodium the exchange capacity per 100 g. of the resin was calculated (last column of Table III).

TABLE III

Na-resin.	H-resin left.	Exchange capacity.
0.0366 g.	0.0282 g.	1229 m.e.
0.0566	0.0423	1209

Table III shows the amount of Na-resin taken for the estimation of adsorbed Na^+ and also the corresponding amount of H-resin left behind. All the samples were dried at 105° . Assuming some arbitrary degree of hydration of the Na^+ and H^+ ions, the following ratios between the weights of Na-resin and H-resin have been calculated. The results together with the experimental values are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

$\frac{\text{Na}_2\text{R}}{(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{R}}$	$\frac{\text{Na}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{R}}{(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{R}}$	$\frac{\text{Na}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4\text{R}}{(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{R}}$	Experimental values.
1.05	1.27	1.49	(a) 1.30 (b) 1.34

The experimental values are closer to the case in which both the H^+ and the Na^+ ions are each hydrated with one molecule of water (column 2). It is possible that Na^+ ions, which are usually hydrated with a larger number of water molecules, have lost most of them at the temperature of the measurement, viz. 105° . The hydration of the three dimensional resins, in which the linkage is through carbon atoms, is likely to be less favourable than the layer lattice siliceous clays. Perhaps for this reason the hydration of the exchangeable cations associated with the resins is also affected, and hence, the lower hydration of Na^+ , as is shown by the above data.

Potentiometric Titration of the Acid-resin with Alkali.—The interaction of the coarse-grained resin with alkali is a slow process, but preliminary experiments have shown that the colloiddally dispersed resin acid can be successfully titrated with alkali and the neutralisation reaction is rapid enough for potentiometric measurements. For these experiments two suspensions of the finely dispersed material were prepared from portions not settling in 20 hours and 8 hours respectively.

The curve shown in Fig. 2 (curve a) was obtained by titrating a 20 hour-suspension of the acid resin (0.58 g./litre) with 0.1069N-NaOH using the hydrogen electrode. The resin after each addition of alkali was vigorously stirred and the E.M.F. remaining constant for 10 to 15 minutes was read as the equilibrium value. It will be seen from the neutralisation curve that it is characterised by two inflexion points. The inflexions are small but fairly marked. Mention has been made earlier that these two inflexions correspond to the neutralisation of the two exchangeable H^+ ions at the two -OH spots of the resorcinol-formaldehyde resin. The acidity corresponding to the first inflexion point is almost exactly half of that corresponding to the second. The resin suspension simulates a dibasic acid character. Corresponding to the second inflexion point, the exchange capacity is equal to 1237 m.e. The apparent pK values of the acid resin are 8.65 and 10.5 respectively. It may be of interest to know how resorcinol itself would behave under similar circumstances. Fig. 3 shows the titration curve of the pure resorcinol, obtained with the help of a Beckmann p_H meter fitted with glass electrode. The close similarity between the two curves is striking, but from the pK values calculated from the half neutralisation points (9.1 and 10.7) it appears that the resin acid is perhaps slightly stronger than pure resorcinol. Also, the acidity of the resorcinol calculated from the second inflexion point corresponds to the formula $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})_2$, where the H^+ ions in the phenolic -OH groups are unhydrated unlike that in the resin made from it.

The neutralisation curve, shown in Fig. 2 (curve c), refers to the resin material obtained by dialysis of the coloured extract of the alkali-treated, 10 hour-cured, coarse

resin. The resulting acid sol (0.36 g./litre) was a reddish brown, stable, colloidal solution. The potentiometric titration was carried out with the help of hydrogen electrode. The titration curve shows two inflexions but at lower p_n 's, as compared with the 20 hours' suspension. The exchange capacity corresponding to the second inflexion point is equal to 1250 m.e.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

Exchange Capacity from Interaction with Alkaline Earth Hydroxides.—Baryta and calcium hydroxide afforded higher exchange capacities than sodium hydroxide with coarse resin. The value was close to the theoretical in the case of the baryta and slightly higher in the case of calcium hydroxide. The possibility of the latter being adsorbed as $-CaOH$ was mentioned by Akeroyd and Broughton (*loc. cit.*). In order to eliminate the effect of carbon dioxide, if any, a titration with calcium hydroxide using the 8 hours' suspension of the acid resin (0.61 g./litre) was carried out potentiometrically by means of hydrogen electrode. The titration (Fig. 2, curve b) was carried out up to the first equivalence point. Thus, there was only one inflexion and the exchange capacity, calculated from double the amount required to reach the first inflexion, is equal to 1220 m.e./100 g. Due to elimination of the effect of carbon dioxide, since under the condition of the experiment carried out in an atmosphere of hydrogen gas, the calculated exchange capacity is slightly lower and is very close to the theoretical exchange capacity. It further shows that calcium hydroxide does not react with the resin acids as $-CaOH$ to any extent.

A comparison of the three curves (Fig. 2) reveals that both the half neutralisation p_n or the pK values and the p_n at which complete neutralisation occurs are lower, the

smaller the size of the particles in the suspension, or, in other words, for the same quantity of the resin the finer fraction exhibits stronger acid function.

Hydrolysis of the Resinates.—The resinates are hydrolysed in aqueous solution to different extents depending on the nature of the cation and, as such, resemble the salts of weak acids. It was observed that the hydrolysis was considerably suppressed in presence of a high cationic concentration. The results recorded in Table V show that the dilute suspensions (0.9293g./litre) of Na- and NH_4 - resinates are more hydrolysable than the Ca-resinate. Unlike the latter the Ba-resinate hydrolyses appreciably. The percentage of hydrolysis of the different resinates at the low concentration of 11.3 m.e. per litre is shown below.

TABLE V

System.	Conc. of cation in supernat. soln. in 60 c.c.	% Dissociation.
Na-Resin	0.3147 m.e.	46.28
Ca-Resin	0.1879	27.63
NH_4 -Resin	0.3481	51.24
Ba-Resin	0.3702	54.44

The experiments were performed with 60 c.c. of the suspension containing 0.05576 g. of H-form of the resin (0.9293 g./litre), i.e. containing $0.05576 \times 12.2 \approx 0.68$ m.e. in 60 c.c.

Exchange Isotherms.—To equal volumes of the resinates having the same colloid content increasing quantities of neutral electrolytes were added. The concentration of the latter generally varied from one-fourth to four times the symmetry concentration. The final volume of the supernatant solution with colloid was in all cases 60 c.c. The analyses of the supernatant liquids were made for both the interacting cations after allowing about two weeks for the equilibration. The experimental data are graphically illustrated in Figs. 4 to 7.

FIG. 4

FIG. 5

The curves apparently do not look like the usual exchange adsorption isotherms. On the other hand, they show marked bends or inflexion points. These inflexions are more marked in those cases where the exchange is of a bivalent cation in the resinate for a monovalent one of the added electrolyte.

FIG. 6

FIG. 7

A proper evaluation of the isotherms can be made in the light of the titration curves reported earlier. The latter have definitely demonstrated the existence of two types of exchange spots varying in their energy of adsorption. It is clear that the cations saturating the resin must have different degrees of exchangeability as a result of the different intensities of bonding of cations on the resin surface. The inflexion points in the isotherms indicate to a greater or less extent this property of the cations. It is to be expected that the difference in the exchangeability will be more easy to follow in cases where the exchangeable cations are comparatively difficult to replace. That this is so is shown by the sharper inflexion points in the curves obtained from the calcium and the barium resins. It is, however, to be noted that in order to establish these inflexions, it is expedient to study the isotherm at an extremely low concentration and follow it up to a relatively high concentration of the added electrolytes. For this reason the electrolytes in these experiments were added at one-fourth of the symmetry concentration, increasing gradually to four times the symmetry concentration.

It will be noticed from these curves that the inflexions occur at the low concentration region and almost at the same equilibrium concentration of the added electro-

lytes for each of the systems. For the systems saturated with the divalent cations this equilibrium concentration is almost the same, but higher than that for the monovalent cation-saturated systems. This follows from the fact that the divalent cations, corresponding to the same region of the exchange spots, are probably more firmly held by such forces as determine their adsorbability and therefore require a larger concentration of the added electrolytes for their replacement.

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